

USING DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES TO PROMOTE TOURISM INDUSTRY

Nasiba Akramova Abdurakhmanovna

Lecturer at Joint Degree Programs Department,
Bukhara State University
Bukhara, Uzbekistan

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13879654>

Abstract: opinions about the importance of digital technologists in the promotion of tourism products are expressed in the thesis. The importance of digital technologies in the development of the current tourism market is increasing day by day. Representatives of the tourism industry prefer to sell their tourist products quickly, taking into account the time factor. It is certainly taking into account the digital technologies that are implementing this quality.

Keywords: digitalization, technology, tourism market, products, marketing, promotion.

The rivalry in the tourism industry is positively impacted by all kinds of products and services. The number of people who wish to travel has significantly increased as a result of these applications. Information technology application in the tourism industry helps tourist organizations operate more efficiently and boosts their production. In summary, information technology applications assist the tourism industry in particular make great strides and contribute positively to the national economy.

In order to consistently continue the comprehensive reforms implemented in our country in the interests of the people, to implement the Strategy of Actions on the five priority directions of the development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021 in the "Year of Science, Enlightenment and Digital Economy Development" The project of the state program was prepared with the participation of the public. In the course of discussions, our people, civil society institutions showed activity, direct dialogues were organized with them through more than a thousand TV and radio channels, and the suggestions made by our citizens were deeply discussed with the participation of specialists and experts in the relevant field. was analyzed. Also, the prospects of tourism development are specified in this decree[3].

When taking into account the size and quantity of employees, it can be generally stated that the tourism sector holds a significant role for nations and all other economic sectors. The tourist industry is one of the sectors with the highest employment rates. The information technology sector has experienced

growth and change, growing into a vast technological field, all thanks to advancements and breakthroughs in the field. Stakeholders and travelers in the industry may view travel differently as a result of these developments and adjustments. People can communicate everywhere these days since information is so easily and quickly accessible, and this need to share knowledge can somewhat help the travel and tourist industry [1].

In the age of digital revolution, travel agencies and locations may encounter difficulties in the road if they do not have a creative management strategy. It is aware that conventional marketing techniques are less successful now than they were in the past. Everything has changed now. To survive, locations and businesses must go digital. The conduct of travelers both before and after their vacation is influenced by these digital capabilities and technological devices. To draw visitors and turn them into devoted patrons, tourism establishments and locations need to offer both the pre-trip and journey experiences. It is becoming more and more crucial to track visitors as they spend time at a facility or destination in order to comprehend their experiences and make sure they are accurately represented in the digital sphere. Time and place are perceived differently in the digital society that results from digital revolution. These are personal shifts that start out in an individual's life and eventually spread throughout all social networks and interactions. Travel is one of the industries it has impacted and demonstrated its presence in the tourism market [2].

Technology is causing significant changes in the worldwide tourist sector. Technology advancements throughout the past ten years have drastically changed how research and reservations for tourism services are made. The primary focus of the strategy for the growth of culture and tourism in future cities is likewise shifting to digital technologies. When digital technologies are used in urban areas, visitors can more easily integrate into the environment and plan their own trips. They can also converse with locals using an earpiece that translates simultaneously and receive personalized recommendations for museums and entertainment venues based on their interests.

Travelers from all over the world now rely heavily on digital travel platforms (Hojeghan, 2016). By 2021, the total value of digital travel transactions worldwide—which include airfare, vehicle rentals, hotels, lodging, and transportation—will reach \$855.07 billion (Urquhart, 2019). Globally, smartphone payment apps and online travel agencies (OTAs) are revolutionizing the travel sector (Liberato, 2018; Matteo, 2019). Because smartphone apps are

readily available and rates are inexpensive, more and more customers are making reservations online. Global travel revenues reached \$694.41 billion in 2018, a 10.4% increase [4].

The following are now the primary avenues for growth in the digital tourist environment:

1. Everybody involved in the tourism sector makes an effort to meet visitors' demands, keeping in mind their unique goals and desires. Entities in the tourism business can use analytical data to get comprehensive knowledge on visitors, which enables them to use customized methods and maximize client satisfaction. Travel agencies must employ cutting-edge data analysis procedures to anticipate client needs, comprehend their complexity, and derive analytical findings with real-world application.

2. Constant advancement of multimedia technologies and content. The tourism business is embracing new methods to promote tourism services and technical standards, which has led to the active development of multimedia content. The variety of multimedia information gives travel service companies all the tools they need to provide customized services to each customer. Innovative tourism technologies that add fresh perspectives and colors to travel are in greater demand. One such example is the "Tour Guide" mobile application. The tourism industry's aggressive adoption of digital technologies facilitates visitors' speedy acclimatization to the industry's standard operating procedures. These methods cover things like booking accommodations, using programs for travel planning, tracking luggage online, and other services [5].

3. The development of a networked information and communication technology system. The creation of "smart cities" is the path that will ultimately decide multiculturalism and the rise in consumer demand. Tourism development prospects are contingent upon the stage-by-stage delivery of goods via several modes of transportation and data analysis, which will indubitably elevate the quality of tailored service. The creation and growth of an interconnected network of information and communication technologies, exemplified by smart cities, will enable the tourism industry to develop more efficiently by giving each visitor the utmost attention and guaranteeing the high-quality satisfaction of their needs [6].

Advances in technology have enabled the export of numerous digitally rendered tourism services to other countries. Because digital technologies do not require the tourism service provider to be physically present in close

proximity to the client, they also lower transaction and communication expenses.

The increased competitiveness among hospitality organizations to capture and attract each customer has made the implementation and use of automated management systems crucial in the tourist sector.

Nowadays, the presence of very big data sets that are hard to structure and manipulate has rendered the use of standard statistical procedures impractical. As a result, big data from contemporary technical digital solutions must be used to develop this industry while accounting for suppliers' and customers' remote locations [7].

The development of different building blocks, services, and mobile applications that enable the performance of functions aimed at improving the system of promoting the national tourism product is made possible by information and communication platforms. According to the national policy for the advancement of digital technologies within the context of tourism, the following areas are given top priority:

- development of cutting-edge technologies to market domestic travel goods on electronic media;
- the creation and deployment of language versions of websites that facilitate easy communication, information sharing, self-service, and navigation for all kinds of travelers, so enhancing the caliber, accessibility, and appeal of services;
- creation of smartphone applications and electronic travel maps that adhere to our nation's international standards. Travelers will have the freedom to plan their own itineraries, make use of the public transportation system in the area, learn about local cultural events and activities, and get deals on a range of excursions;
- verify the dependability of the electronic system used to track the caliber of tourism services and assign a level of quality to each region's tourism amenities [6];

The active development of digital technologies in the tourism industry entails the concurrent development of tourism-related subjects within the framework of acquiring digital competencies and skills, adapting to new technological conditions, and creating new forms of interaction, communication, and work methodologies. The way we live, spend our free time, travel, and enjoy life have all undergone significant change as a result of digital technologies.

References:

1. Erkayeva Gulbakhor Panjiyevna, Ways of effective use of mobile innovative technologies in the development of tourism potential, "Economics and Innovative Technologies" scientific electronic journal, 5/2022
2. Rakhimov Z.O. The development of new types of digitized tourism in the digital economy. / International online scientific-practical conference on the topic "Prospects for the development of innovation-investment processes in tourism" held at SamISI. (June 3, 2020) – Samarkand: SamISI, 2020.
3. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated 02.03.2020 No. PF-5953 - "Strategy of Actions on five priority areas of development of the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2017-2021
4. Vishnevskaya E. V. (2019), The impact of digital technologies on the development of the tourism market. Research Result. Business and Service Technologies, 5(3)
5. Volkov S.K. Tourism as a sector of the creative economy [Electronic resource] // Creative Economy. - 2021. - Vol. 15. - No. 5.
6. Izyurov, D. O., & Fesenko, O. P. (2024). DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN TOURISM. Economy and Society, (5-2 (120)), 1039-1045.
7. Oborin M.S. Directions for the development of the digital tourism environment [Electronic resource] // Service in Russia and abroad. 2023. No. 1 (103).
8. Akramova, N. (2024). BUKHARA'S TOURISM RENAISSANCE: LEVERAGING HERITAGE, BRANDING, AND SUSTAINABILITY FOR ECONOMIC GROWTH. Innovative Society: Problems, Analysis and Development Prospects (Spain), 5, 8-12.

